

TERASUN

Towards Terawatt Production of c-Si Solar Photovoltaics

D1.15 Scientific & technical plan, execution report M7 - M12

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General Information

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WP # and title	WP1 Team alignment and project management
Contributors	ALL partners
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Project Profile

Table 1 Key figures of the TERASUN project.

Programme	Horizon Europe
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Topic	HORIZON-CL5-2023-D3-02-11
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Coordinator	IDENER

TERASUN Consortium Partners

Table 2 List of partners in the TERASUN project including acronym and country.

#	Partner	Short	CO
1	IDENER R&D AGRUPACION DE INTERES ECONOMICO	IDE	ES
2	Fraunhofer Institute for Solar Energy Systems	ISE	DE
3	PV2+	PV2+	DE
4	Commissariat a l'énergie atomique et aux énergies alternatives	CEA	FR
5	Technische Universiteit Delft	TUD	NL
6	RINA Consulting – Centro Sviluppo Materiali SPA	RINA-CSM	IT
7	Fyzikalni Ustav AV CR V.V.I	FZU	CZ

Version	Date	Name, Organization	Comment
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Executive Summary

The objective of this deliverable is to give a concise report of the progress of the Terasun project, i.e. the work packages and their associated tasks, during the period M7-M12. It is structured by work package and each section includes the review of status and outlook (next steps), as well as an updated list of risks.

In this next phase of the project, a consortium meeting was organised at TUD where the consortium partners were able to discuss face-to-face and align their activities. It was also the opportunity to welcome our new partner FZU and thereby successfully conclude their integration in the Terasun team. Besides, the development in all WPs continued achieving certain KPIs, e.g. in WP2 $R_{600} < 10\%$ for a nano-modulated pyramidal texture. In WP3, we report on the advances of the development of In-free TCOs (AZO and SnO_2) using different deposition methods: sputtering (co-sputtering) and slot-die coating. Furthermore, using sputtered MoOx and Boron-based plasma treatments have yielded 21.24% maximum power conversion efficiency small-sized cells on 4-inch wafers. The thermal evaporation MoOx process on the other hand yielded 23.94% on 4-inch and 22.03% on M2 with tools closer to industrial standards. Good passivation levels—minority carrier lifetime of > 2.5 ms and implied V_{oc} of 745 mV—were obtained for small and large textures on M6 wafers. Regarding the Cu-plating development, we report on advances obtained with FlexTrail-printing and the laser-based approach leading to fine lines and comparable results as obtained for screen-printing. The activities in WP4 started with the planning of the tasks contained in the work package. In WP5, the first version of the Terasun DST database has been released and the LCA/LCC strategy has been defined. And finally, in WP6 we report on the SMARTIES seminar held in collaboration with Terasun's sister projects BURST and SiLEAN as well as updates of the website.

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Table of Abbreviations

Abbreviation	Description
ARC	Anti-Reflective Coating
AZO	Aluminium-doped Zinc Oxide
CINEA	EU Climate, Environment and Infrastructure Executive Agency
CM	Consortium Meeting
c-Si	Crystalline silicon
Cz	Czochralski
D	Deliverable
DMP	Data Management Plan
DST	Decision Support Tool
ECM	Electrochemical Machining
GA	Grant Agreement
IBC	Interdigitated back-contacted
ITO	Indium Tin Oxide
KoM	Kick-off Meeting
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
LCA	Life Cycle Assessment
LCC	Life Cycle Costing
LCOE	Levelised Cost of Electricity
M	Month
MST	Modulated Surface Texture
PMP	Project Management Plan
QSSPC	Quasi-Steady-State Photoconductance
RF	Radio Frequency
SEM	Scanning Electron Microscope
SHJ	Silicon Heterojunction
SnO ₂	Tin oxide
T	Task
TCO	Transparent Conductive Oxide
TLM	Transfer Length Method
WP	Work Package

1. Work package 1

1.1. Executive summary

Executive Summary	
Main results	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • First scientific & technical plan, execution report M1–M6 submitted. • Successful integration of FZU as new partner including getting the required amendment approved.

DV#	Title	Status
D1.6	Scientific & technical plan, execution report M1-M6	Submitted

MS#	Title	Status
No MS planned for reporting period M7 – M12.		
MS7	Half of the project executed; Review of the process with the EC	Due M19

1.2. Tasks: Status

1.2.1. T1.1 Technical project management and coordination

During the current reporting period M7–M12, the technical project management and coordination relied mainly on regular WP meetings to align all partners. Besides the WP meetings the M12 Consortium Meeting was held at TUD Delft on May 22nd – 23rd, 2025. This meeting gave the consortium partners the opportunity to present the status of their individual tasks, discuss and plan upcoming activities. The meetings and the regular exchange within the consortium made sure that all the due deliverables were submitted on time:

- D1.6 Scientific & technical plan, execution report M1-M6
- D2.1 Interim report on lab-scale nano-structuring processes for c-Si wafers
- D3.2 Report on lab scale MO deposition processes
- D5.2 First release of TERASUN DST database

Moreover, as reported before, the proposal to add *FYZIKALNI USTAV AV CR V.V.I. (FZU)*, Prague has been accepted and the required amendments to the Grant Agreement were applied by IDE and accepted by the European Commission. In addition to this, by signing the accession form, FZU retroactively joined the TERASUN project in *M9 (February 2025)*.

1.2.2. T1.2 Financial and administrative project management

Monitoring of financial and administrative aspects of the TERASUN project has been ongoing. Intermediate financial reports have been collected from all the partners. Furthermore, the Hop-On proposal that was submitted in reporting period M1-M6 to add FZU to the TERASUN consortium has been granted. Adding the new partner (incl. budget updates etc.) required an amendment to the Grant Agreement which has been submitted and applied successfully. As of M12 of the TERASUN project this amendment is in force and FZU has been retroactively added to the consortium starting from M9.

The partners have provided this data and details will be reported in *D1.5 Economic progress report M1 - M12* (due M14).

1.2.3. T1.3 Project progress and quality monitoring, risk management and evaluation

The progress of the TERASUN has been continuously monitored throughout the reporting period both in online meetings (via MS Teams) and during the recent Consortium Meeting hosted by TUD. The reports (presentations) of the individual WPs are stored on the projects [SharePoint](#). Besides certain technical challenges in some of the tasks the consortium continues to deliver high quality results. New risks have been highlighted during the Consortium meeting:

- **Integration of FZU into the ongoing TERASUN project:** Related to the activities in WP1, the addition of a new partner (FZU) to the consortium poses the risk of successful integration. To achieve this, FZU has been added to all the meetings, was present at the Consortium Meeting hosted by TUD and will host the upcoming Consortium Meeting (M18). This risk has been added with the amendment of the Grant Agreement related to the addition of FZU to the project consortium.
- **Application of the Raman based light-trapping characterization on textured crystalline silicon solar cells:** Related to the newly added task of FZU in WP3, T3.7, this risk has been added with the amendment of the Grant Agreement related to the addition of FZU to the project consortium.
- **The photoluminescence spectrum may overshadow the Raman signal necessary for proper interpretation of the measurements:** Related to the newly added task of FZU in WP3, T3.7, this risk has been added with the amendment of the Grant Agreement related to the addition of FZU to the project consortium.
- **Passivation of nano-structured c-Si surface:** In T2.1 the development of plasma-based nano-structuring processes has made promising advances for the modification of the micro-scale textures. However, a *significant* challenge remains: the passivation of the increasingly rough c-Si wafer surface. This is to be added to the list of risks throughout the project.

Personnel-related risks have been assessed through a dedicated questionnaire directly with TERASUN's executive board and no additional risks have been identified. Neither did any of the potential risks materialise.

1.2.4. T1.4 Data management and open science

As the guidelines for data management and open science have already been defined in D1.3, no further action was taken during the current reporting period. The DMP (D1.3) will be updated in M18 and at the end of the project (M36).

1.2.5. T1.5 KPI definition, evaluation, and validation

After defining the list of KPIs in *D1.4 KPIs for the TERASUN technologies M4*, continuous KPI evaluation took place in each of the project's WPs. Some KPIs have been reached already as will be discussed in the WP sections. The report on KPIs will be updated in M24 and at the end of the project (M36).

1.3. Tasks: Outlook

In the reporting period M13-M18 project management will focus on preparing the upcoming project review and on assembling the review report for the European Commission. This will include not only technical details but also the financial and administrative (project management and risk management) aspects of the TERASUN project.

1.4. Risks

Four additional risks associated with adding FZU as a new member of the TERASUN consortium have been added to the list (see above). These risks describe the risk of full integration of FZU into the running project and the application of FZU's expertise in Raman spectroscopy and photoluminescence measurements. To avoid the materialisation of these risks, FZU has been integrated into all the relevant project-related communication channels and will host the next consortium meeting. Furthermore, bilateral discussions and sample exchange between the other partners and FZU has been encouraged during the M12 Consortium Meeting. Finally, the risk reflecting the challenge of passivating the nano-structured c-Si surfaces (TUD, T2.1) has also been added as mentioned above.

1.5. Meetings in M7-M12

The *Consortium Meeting M12*, organised by TUD, took place end of May 2025 and was held at the Technical University of Delft. During the meeting the latest updates of the TERASUN developments were presented and the upcoming activities discussed. As the first in-person project meeting, it also was a good opportunity for the entire consortium to get to know each other personally and for the team members from FZU to be included.

Besides the CM, during the reporting period *WP Meetings* were held to update the consortium partners on a regular basis and organise the next steps in each WP. These meetings also served for monitoring progress of the tasks.

Figure 2 TERASUN Consortium Meeting M12.

2. Work package 2

2.1. Executive summary

Executive Summary	
Main results	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Plasma etching process successfully applied • KPI reflectance at 600 nm < 10% achieved • Small-sized pyramids obtained with wet etching process • T2.3.1 is successfully completed • First characterizations of the round robin samples were performed.

DV#	Title	Status
D2.1	Interim report on lab-scale nano-structuring processes for c-Si wafers	Submitted

MS#	Title	Status
MS5	Nanostructures achieved at lab scale	Achieved

2.2. Tasks: Status

2.2.1. *T2.1 Plasma-based nano-structuring process for modulation of micro-scale textures*

In this period, to minimize environmental concerns, SF₆ is removed from the process gases, which yields in NF₃/Ar/O₂ mixture as the gas precursor.

To provide with uniform etching of the wafer, in other words no angular reflection difference, the etching pressure varied from 0.2-1.0 mbar. At 0.4 mbar, the uniform etching has been observed. As seen in Figure 3, tilting the wafer does not change the colour or brightness as in 0.8 mbar case. Moreover, the reflectance goes below 4% in the wavelength range of 750-1000 nm. At 600 nm, reflectance is around 5%.

Figure 3 Pictures of c-Si surface after SF₆-free RIE under different pressure: 0.8 mbar (left) and 0.4 mbar (centre). The difference is apparent in the dark colours for tilted samples. Reflectance spectra of the surface under 0.4 mbar (RIE) and RPT as reference.

To conclude, plasma-etching showed 5% reflectance at 600 nm wavelength, successfully achieving the KPI of < 10% reflectance. The potential current density increases when compared to random pyramid texturing is simulated to be 3.72 mA/cm². Furthermore, to minimize environmental concerns, SF₆ is removed from the process gases, which yields in NF₃/Ar/O₂ mixture as the gas precursor. Details could be found in the deliverable D2.1.

2.2.2. T2.2 Wet-chemical etching process for nano-structuring of c-Si wafers

In this period, we tried a more stable texture additive and varied the saw damage etching (SDE) time before texturing to get a smoother surface prior to texturing (Figure 4). The long SDE time smoothens the surface by enlarging the etch dips.

Figure 4 Confocal images for random pyramids on Cz-Si(n) for two additives and for two saw damage removal depths prior to texturing. Short removal etch leads to a thick wafer and long removal etch to a smooth tinner wafer. The texturing on a smooth surface leads to more homogenous pyramids.

We counted the pyramids on the confocal images and present it as a histogram for the pyramid base area. The Nano-2 texture exhibits pyramid base areas smaller than $2 \mu\text{m}^2$, the mean pyramid base area is $1.5 \mu\text{m}^2$. The standard texture features bigger pyramids with a mean pyramid base area of $5.0 \mu\text{m}^2$ (Figure 5). We were able to reach more homogeneous texture on a smoother surface. The next step is to produce solar cells with these textures. The mean total reflection at 600 nm is $10.2 \pm 0.1\%$ measured by a handheld spectrometer (Ci64 x-rite). We did not reach a reflection below 10% because we did not want to shape the pyramids differently or add something to the pyramid tips, which would reduce passivation quality.

Figure 5 Pyramid base area histogram for two different texture processes and for two different saw damage etching times (Short and long SDE) prior to texturing. Evaluation by Texana by Fraunhofer ISE.

2.2.3. T2.3 Nanophotonic structures for module cover glass

In addition to the simulations from the previous reporting period, a triple anti-reflective coating (ARC) was investigated as approximation to a graded-index layer. In combination with texture, this could enhance the in-coupling for diffuse light by another 2%, on top of the 3.5% achievable with the single layer ARC.

Taking also fabrication aspects and durability into account, the texture in combination with the single layer ARC is seen as the best solution for the project. With this result, T2.3.1 is completed.

In T2.3.2, the following process flow was investigated: Deposition of etching mask, laser ablation of the etching mask, etching of the glass structure under the mask opening, removal of the etching mask. First results (inverted spherical caps with pitch 25 μm) shown in Figure 6 are very promising.

Figure 6 Confocal microscopy image of etched glass surface (texture pitch: 25 μm)

2.2.4. T2.4 Characterisation of wafer surface structure and nanophotonic structures on glass

During this period, the first characterizations of the round robin samples were performed.

Samples of textured wafers are characterized by reflectometer/spectrophotometer (reflectance), optical microscope (pyramid size distribution, density, mean height, etc) and SEM (surface morphology, pyramid density, etc). The textured samples are measured at CEA, TUD and ISE site. A first comparison of reflectance measurement is presented on Figure 7. The reflectance spectrum is very similar, and we can notice very slightly different probably due to calibration. The effective reflectance is calculated by AM1.5g standard spectrum according to IEC 60904: CEA and ISE are using this reference.

The pyramid size distribution on sample C was determined by ISE using Optical microscope and home-made image processing (Figure 8).

	Reflectance @600 nm	Reflectance @950 nm	Effective reflectance (350-1000 nm)
CEA	12,10%	10,28%	12,27%
TUD	12,38%	10,23%	to be calculated
ISE	12,48%	10,64%	to be calculated

Figure 7 Reflectance spectrum of sample A and reflectance value at different wavelength and effective reflectance

Figure 8 Characterization of morphology on sample C at ISE site.

Table 3 presents a comparison of CEA and ISE: depending on observation site, it is possible to observe difference in terms of pyramid size. Usually, the type of characterization is used to follow the wet process and capture a drift.

Table 3 Morphology characterization – comparison ISE and ISE results on pyramid density measurement

Partners	Pyramid density (Nb/mm ²)	Mean Pyramid height (μm)	Mean Pyramid size sqrt(base) (μm)	Min Pyramid size (μm)	Max Pyramid size (μm)
ISE	250 253	1,3	1,9	0,7	4,7
CEA	322 640	1,2	1,6	0,4	3,1

During the first two months, FZU started work on Task T2.4.1 by setting up the experimental infrastructure for advanced characterization. We have performed initial test measurements to validate our optical characterization approach (Raman spectroscopy and hyperspectral PL) on early samples received from

TUD. These first measurements will allow us to optimize measurement protocols, assess signal quality, and identify key parameters relevant for subsequent direct, non-contact characterization of light-trapping properties.

2.3. Tasks: Outlook

- **T2.1 and T2.2:** Process developments are going to continue, upscaling to industrial sized wafers is going to start.
- **T2.3:** Further developments will address the optimization of the texture geometry and the combination with a nanoporous ARC.
- **T2.4:** Data collection from all partners is going to be continued for Round Robin. The textured samples will be sent to FZU to test on their advanced characterization.
- **T2.4.1:** Standard samples, crystalline silicon wafers with a well-defined pyramid on the surface, will be supplied by ISE and CEA. These will be used for the comparison and calibration of the measurement systems.

2.4. Risks

The KPI of $R_{600} < 10\%$ has been achieved using dry etching processes (T2.1). Nevertheless, successful passivation of these new surface structures remains challenging and will be one of the objectives for the coming months (T3.5).

3. Work package 3

3.1. Executive summary

Executive Summary	
Main results	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A homogeneous coverage by AZO slot die on texturization of the surface has been performed • Good electrical properties of the AZO layer, compatible to solar cells integration has been reached • SnO₂ development is ongoing: a sheet resistance of SnO₂ matrix with no doping is measurable • Using the sputtering method, currently a maximum efficiency of 21.24% has been achieved for 4-inch MoOx cells with plasma treatment with Boron (PTB) • Applying the thermal evaporation method, 23.94% power conversion efficiency has been achieved on 4-inch wafer for MoOx cells with 4-inch-compatible tools. When employing M2-compatible tools—that are closer to industrial standards—an efficiency of 22.03% was obtained on a 4-inch wafer without plasma treatment (PT) • Good passivation level has been reached for small and large texture on M6 wafer area: the minor carrier lifetime has improved from 1.5 ms to 2.5 ms, and the implied Voc has increased from 730 mV to 745 mV. • For the FlexTrail-printing patterning of the top Al layer, process settings were found to pattern fine lines in the Al layer. • Concerning the approach using a laser patterning and Cu plating the J-V has shown a wide spreading of the values but that for some cells the Voc are comparable between the metallization

DV#	Title	Status
D3.2	Report on lab scale MO deposition processes	Planned M12

MS#	Title	Status
No MS planned for reporting period M7 – M12, nor for M13 – M18.		

3.2. Tasks: Status

3.2.1. T3.1 Large-area slot-die coating process for In-free TCOs

For this task, the slot-die coating equipment was modified to be compatible with M2 wafers by replacing the small coating head (4 cm outlet) with a larger one suitable for full-wafer coverage. However,

preliminary tests with the new head highlighted significant reproducibility issues, and persistent hardware malfunctions limited the use of the system. As a result, formulation optimization activities were carried out using bar coating, which proved to be a more stable and reliable alternative for this phase. This approach enabled continued progress on material development while RINA works with the supplier to resolve the slot-die system's hardware problems.

Regarding the subtask T3.1.2 (SHJ-compatible thermal or laser-based post-processing for slot-die TCOs), the replacement of tubular furnace is done. Some preliminary tests were conducted on samples provided by CEA, in particular M2 textured and passivated wafers.

Figure 9: Morphological distribution of the coating on passivated samples provided by CEA

The coatings applied as described above, were investigated by SEM (Figure 9), which showed a homogeneous, likely conformal coverage. The conformality of the coating, i.e. the fact that it follows the pyramidal structure of the texture, remains to be confirmed. Further TEM/SEM assessments are planned for future experiments.

The formulation optimization phase of the sol-gel used for the coating has been completed using the bar coating technique. The next steps will involve employing this formulation to obtain homogeneous layers via slot-die coating on M2-sized passivated surfaces provided by CEA. The goal is to deposit a conformal layer on micron-scale textures. The goal is to deposit conformal layer on micron-scale texture. All the thermal treatment will be performed in the tubular furnace considering the usage of different gas mixture to avoid humidity related issues.

3.2.2. T3.2 Development of sputter-deposited In-free TCOs

Regarding *SnO₂ development*, the first intrinsic SnO₂ depositions (variation of O₂ % and deposition temperature, RT and < 200°C) were performed: the layers were too resistive. The co-sputtering tests (SnO₂ and doped target) was realized to dope the layer in DC and RF mode. The variation of power and the variation of the doping were also tested but for all the experimental conditions, the sheet resistance of the material was not measurable. So, we decided to work first on SnO₂ matrix without doping and try to reach a sheet resistance measurable.

The screening of process parameters has been realized: variation of gas mixture and variation of total pressure. The best condition (Figure 10) is for #5 condition of plasma but far away from the attended specifications for a TCO

Figure 10 SnO2 matrix: resistivity and transmittance in different process conditions

The next steps are to improve the electrical properties of the layer and start co sputtering to dope the layer.

Concerning **AZO development**, the process activity restarts for the project based on T. Gageot thesis (see Poster, EU-PVSEC 2025). The screening of process parameters has been realized: variation of sputtering power, deposition pressure and gas mixing.

The variation of sputtering power has shown that the mobility value μ is stable between 11.0 and 11.6 $\text{cm}^2 \cdot \text{V}^{-1} \cdot \text{s}^{-1}$ (Literature: 24 $\text{cm}^2 \cdot \text{V}^{-1} \cdot \text{s}^{-1}$) and the resistivity is driven by the carrier concentration.

The variation of the deposition pressure was studied (Figure 11). The resistivity (R_{sheet}) is driven by higher mobility ($\approx 11 \text{ cm}^2 \cdot \text{V}^{-1} \cdot \text{s}^{-1}$) and higher carrier concentration ($\approx 3 \cdot 10^{20} \text{ cm}^{-3}$). The transmission and absorption values are stable with the deposition pressure. But the absorption is still high.

Figure 11 Effect of deposition pressure on AZO electrical properties and optical properties

The study of gas mixing has shown that the O₂ gas variation has a slight impact on optical properties due to lower carrier concentration.

The current developments have confirmed the good electrical properties of the AZO, compatible to solar cells integration. The optical properties of the material are under the performances to the material of reference (Thesis T. Gageot 2024). The losses must be evaluated by optical simulation in the next steps.

The next steps are to perform solar cells integration with pure AZO layer and test of capping layer (with thin ITO or dielectric layer), and to evaluate the optical losses by optical simulation.

3.2.3. T3.3 Metal oxide deposition process for SHJ solar cells

Applying the thermal evaporation method, 23.94% power conversion efficiency has been achieved on 4-inch wafer for MoO_x cells with 4-inch-compatible tools. When employing M2-compatible tools—that are closer to industrial standards—an efficiency of 22.03% was obtained on a 4-inch wafer without plasma treatment (PT). However, further optimization of deposition parameters for each layer is still required. Initial results for 2×2 cm² cells on M2+ wafer reached an efficiency of 14.48% in the first run using screen printing.

Using the sputtering method, currently a maximum efficiency of 21.24% has been achieved for 4-inch MoO_x cells with plasma treatment with Boron (PTB). The J-V parameters with comparison to thermal evaporated method is shown in Table 4. To minimize the sputtering damage, sputtering parameters, including argon flow, sputtering power, and power supply methods (DC or RF), interface treatments and the underlying hydrogenated intrinsic amorphous silicon ((i)a-Si:H) film were optimized. The precursors prepared with optimized deposition parameters demonstrated promising carrier lifetime and implied V_{oc} (iV_{oc}), significantly mitigating sputtering-induced damage. Details could be found in the deliverable D3.2.

Table 4 Average J-V parameters of MoO_x based SHJ solar cells with different deposition methods on 4-inch tools

	V_{oc} [mV]	J_{sc} [mA/cm²]	FF [%]	Efficiency [%]
Thermal MoO _x with PTB	717	40.88	81.26	23.81
Sputtered MoO _x with PTB	677.7	39.53	79.27	21.24

3.2.4. T3.4 Cu-plating for SHJ solar cells

M2 and M6 HJT precursors presenting different texture and coated with TCO were received by PV2+ and divided in groups (Figure 12) before further metallization. For the reference metallization with screen-printing, the results are presented below in Task 3.5). The other wafers were further coated by a PVD metal stack with top Al.

Metallization / TXT -->	M6				M2		
	ISE	ISE	ISE	INES	ISE	ISE	ISE
	Std.	nano-1	nano-2	Std.	Std.	nano-1	nano-2
Screen-printing Ag	5	7	7	7	4	8	8
Laser + Plating	7	9	9	9			
ECM/FlexTrail + Plating	4				4		

Figure 12 Experiment plan for metallization on HJT precursors (screen-printing and Cu plating)

For the FlexTrail-printing patterning of the top Al layer a functionalization of the Al was tested to get reproducible results on the full wafer area. Settings were then found to pattern fine lines in the Al layer (Figure 13) with this technique. Some cells were then plated and further metallized as well as J-V characterized (see in next section).

Figure 13 Microscopic top views of the FlexTrail-printing lines patterned on the M2 HJT wafers with top Al layer

Concerning the approach using a laser patterning and Cu plating, a laser power variation was first implemented to pattern correctly the Al masking layer (Figure 14). For some laser power the patterning went well, and Cu plating was successful. However, a second batch was produced implementing an optimized PVD metal stack and further optimized laser settings to reduce the laser damages characterized by PL and being comparable to the SP reference. The J-V results in Figure 15 show a wide spreading of the values but that for some cells the Voc are comparable between the metallization. However, for FlexTrail, the Voc are relatively low maybe due to shunts as well as the efficiencies. There TLM measurements show a spreading of the ρ_c between 1-2.5 m Ω .cm² so that another batch may be necessary to solve remaining issues. For the other cells metallized by laser and plating an improvement of FF is expected for the ongoing 3rd batch due to laser issues before.

Figure 14 Microscopic top view of the laser patterning and subsequent Cu plating on the different M6 HJT precursors

Figure 15 Microscopic top view of a plated Cu finger on the M6 HJT precursors after PV2+ metallization and measured Voc and efficiency of the different solar cells from batch 2 depending on the metallization

Further process optimization is ongoing to reach the full potential of these HJT solar cells with the 3rd batch as well as one new HJT wafers in preparation by CEA-INES and FH-ISE.

3.2.5. T3.5 High-quality passivation for advanced c-Si textures

This task is linked to T2.2 (WP2) and T3.4 (see above). In the prior report: we presented results of lifetime samples from the first batch and identified improvement potential. The cells from this batch achieved only efficiencies in the range of 22.0 to 22.5%. With slightly similar results for smaller pyramids compared to the reference. In the follow up batch, we have optimized the process to enhance passivation quality and uniformity for the reference texture with a 3 µm pyramid size. This includes transferring the PECVD and PVD processes from reference pyramids to sub-micron pyramids (1.0 down to 0.5 µm). Our findings indicate that the duration of the SDE, whether short (S) or long (L), and texture size (0.5, 1.0 or 3.0 µm) has only a minor impact on passivation quality (slightly improved values for the smallest pyramids). Additionally, we have adapted the PVD process to achieve a consistent effective TCO thickness across the different textures.

Figure 16 Lifetime and iVoc graph and a PL image

As a result, compared to the first batch, the minor carrier lifetime has improved from 1.5 ms to 2.5 ms, and the implied Voc has increased from 730 mV to 745 mV. The next step will be the metallization of the samples. With the adapted processes more samples for plating experiments will be prepared (T3.4).

3.2.6. T3.6 Characterisation of TCOs, metallisation, MOs and passivation

During this period, the list of the characterization equipment of partners was completed with FZU equipment (Table 5).

Table 5 List of FZU characterization equipment

FZU characterisation Equipment
Raman and PL
Raman and PL in nitrogen GB
AFM
AFM in nitrogen GB
SEM +EDX
low absorption spectroscopies
PLQY
TRPL
PL imaging
Ellipsometer

Concerning the round robin, CEA provides:

- ITO samples for thickness measurement, 4PP, Hall effect, spectrophotometer.
- TLM samples to compares contact resistance measurements
- Silver cell M2 BB6 for TUD J-V tester

All ITO samples and TLM samples were measured at CEA site and sent to ISE.

Sample	Average thickness [nm]	n at 633 nm	n at 1 000 nm	k at 633 nm	k at 1 000 nm
ITO-1	97,15	2,018	1,934	0,019	0,044
ITO-2	98,04	2,010	1,925	0,021	0,046

Figure 17 ITO samples: ellipsometer data and transmission data from CEA equipment.

The next steps are to perform data collections of the round robin samples, to compare J-V tester data, to generate reference cells for metallization characterization (CEA and ISE).

3.2.7. T3.7 Profiling and thickness inhomogeneity measurement

During the first two months, when FZU is involved in the project, we have started work on the planned tasks. FZU has begun applying the precise Raman-based technique for determining the thickness of a-Si/nc-Si films with sub-nanometre thickness resolution, as used for back-contacted SHJ Si solar cells. We have also started setting up the faster, photoluminescence-based technique, which is highly relevant for in-line process characterization. To further improve the precision of the thickness calculations, we have ordered a hyperspectral imaging camera.

The thickness imaging method will be optimized for other thin films, such as AlO_x, and MO_x. In addition, we have started exploring the use of Raman spectroscopy to obtain structural information about the passivation films. Since the underlying crystalline silicon wafer is highly Raman active, we will primarily use a UV laser for Raman excitation. The UV light is completely absorbed in the thin silicon film, effectively eliminating the c-Si Raman signal and allowing direct characterization of the passivation layer.

In this early phase of the project for FZU, we have received the first samples from TUD, which will enable us to validate and refine our experimental methods.

3.3. Tasks: Outlook

- **T3.1:** The next steps will be to adapt the slot-die precursor material and test the process on textured wafer. The goal is to deposit conformal layer on micron-scale texture. All the thermal treatment will be performed in the tubular furnace considering the usage of different gas mixture to avoid humidity related issues
- **T3.2: SnO₂ layers:** improve the electrical properties of the layer and start co sputtering to dope the layer. **AZO material optimization:** perform solar cells integration with pure AZO layer and test of capping layer (with thin ITO or dielectric layer) and evaluate the optical losses by optical simulation.
- **T3.3:** optimization of sputtered MoO_x layers on 4-inch (current batch), Implementing Cu-plating into thermal MoO_x cells on M2+ and implementation PTB process on M2+, upscaling (from 2cm*2cm, to 4cm*4cm, and full area)
- **T3.4:** Further process optimization is ongoing to reach the full potential of these HJT solar cells with the 3rd batch as well as one new HJT wafers in preparation by CEA-INES and FH-ISE.
- **T3.5:** The next step will be the metallization of the samples (long and short SDE). With the adapted processes more samples for plating experiments will be prepared (T3.4).
- **T3.6:** The next steps are to perform data collections of the round robin samples, to compare J-V tester data, to generate reference cells for metallization characterization (CEA and ISE)
 - Provide ITO samples (CEA) for round robin characterization (thickness measurement, 4PP measurement, Hall effect and spectrophotometer measurement)
 - Define TLM samples (CEA)
 - Provide M2 silver cell to TUD for J-V tester to test it
- **T3.7:** The thickness imaging method will be optimized for other thin films, such as AlO_x, and MO_x. The use of Raman spectroscopy to obtain structural information about the passivation films will be explored.

3.4. Risks

As mentioned in WP2, even though the KPI for reflectance of textured c-Si wafers has been achieved using dry etching processes (T2.1), the challenge remains to properly passivate these new structures. The TERASUN team will focus on this in the coming months.

4. Work package 4

4.1. Executive summary

WP4 has started in M11 with the planning of the activities that will be addressed in the different tasks. At Fraunhofer ISE the processes for texturing and passivation from WP2 and WP3 will be implemented in solar cells. Experiments for this implementation are currently running. For this purpose, the consortium meeting was used but also an initial online meeting.

Executive Summary	
Main results	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> No results to be reported yet

4.2. Tasks: Status

4.2.1. *T4.1 Applying TERASUN cell components to SHJ solar cells*

The first cell components to be integrated into SHJ solar cells is the development of new nano textures and improved passivation layers, as described in WP2 and WP3 above. The correlating batch has been started with the start of Task 4.1 and will be continued in the next weeks, to investigate the effectivity on full solar cells.

4.2.2. *T4.2 TERASUN components applied to PV modules*

Task 4.2 has not yet started. It will be addressing the implementation of successfully demonstrated cell components following Task 4.1.

4.2.3. *T4.3 Characterisation of cells and modules*

For task 4.3, a round robin of reference samples has been started between the institutes, to align about the measured cell efficiencies at different sites. This will help to make the developments at different partners comparable and accelerate the development cycles.

4.3. Tasks: Outlook

As the work package has just started, most of the work is still ahead. We will closely monitor the developments in WP2 and WP3, to swiftly integrate promising developments into cell and module level and get reasonable benchmarks for the targeted overall goals.

4.4. Risks

No additional risks have been identified for WP4.

5. Work package 5

5.1. Executive summary

Executive Summary	
Main results	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Successful submission of D5.2 First release of TERASUN DST database • LCA/LCC strategy defined

DV#	Title	Status
D5.2	First release of TERASUN DST database	Submitted
D5.4	First version of the TERASUN DST	Planned M14

MS#	Title	Status
MS6	Initial version of TERASUN DST	Planned M14

5.2. Tasks: Status

5.2.1. *T5.1 Data collection of materials and processes used for TERASUN PV devices*

The data collection from the technical work packages WP2-4 was prepared, however, since T5.2 only started in M12, the strategy for data collection could not be finalised. Hence, to be as efficient as possible and keep the overhead for the WP leaders as small as possible, no further actions were taken. Once T5.2 has advanced with the planning of the economic, environmental and sustainability analysis and the list of parameters to request from each partner has been finalised, data will be collected.

5.2.2. *T5.2 Economic, environmental and sustainability data analysis and evaluation*

This task started in M12 with the definition of an efficient approach of how to address the LCA and LCC assessments within the TERASUN project. The strategy of how to approach the task has been discussed among the partners involved (ISE, CEA, TUD, IDE) which concluded in the plan of using the article of Roffeis *et al.*¹ as reference. The authors report on the environmental performance of perovskite-on-silicon tandem solar cells and a full life cycle assessment (LCA) of industrially manufactured modules of this technology. As outlined in Figure 18 in TERASUN a comprehensive LCA and life cycle costing (LCC) will be done for this reference SHJ process, adhering to the standard four-step LCA and LCC framework.

¹ Roffeis et al., Sustainable Energy & Fuels, 2022 ([DOI](#))

1. Goal and scope definition
2. Inventory analysis
3. Impact assessment
4. Results

Initially, the objective and boundaries of the study are determined, specifying the scope, processes, lifecycle stages, and impact categories to be evaluated. Following this, an inventory analysis is conducted using data from project partners and supplemented with information from databases like ecoinvent and GaBi, as well as academic research. This analysis considers inputs such as materials and energy, and outputs including emissions and waste. Lastly, the impact assessment is performed with openLCA software, quantifying environmental and economic impacts from the inventory's data.

Figure 18 LCA/LCC strategy in TERASUN.

Following the LCA/LCC of the reference process, a sensitivity analysis will assess the impact of TERASUN's potential process innovations on environmental and economic outcomes. Process parameters will be varied and evaluated through life cycle assessments and cost analyses to determine their effects. The findings will help to train models that will be implemented in the TERASUN DST, aiding stakeholders in design and decision-making.

Figure 19 Project and consortium structure of governance

5.2.3. T5.3 Stakeholder decision support tool (DST)

The development of the TERASUN DST has advanced significantly. Using state-of-the-art tools (PostgreSQL, .NET Framework and Docker), the team at IDE developed the database model forming the backbone of the TERASUN DST and prepared everything for training the models based on the output of the LCA/LCC analysis (T5.2). These models will later be used in the DST for optimisation purposes. The IDE team also prepared the deployment of the full application e.g. via the TERASUN website using Docker. The full report can be found in *D5.2 First release of TERASUN DST database*.

5.3. Tasks: Outlook

In the next six months, the team will commence with organising data collection after defining the parameters to be collected. Following this, LCA/LCC assessments for the benchmark process will be executed, alongside a thorough sensitivity analysis to ascertain the impact of variable factors. The final step involves the definition and calibration of input and output parameters, train the predictive models, and integrate them in the TERASUN DST to aid stakeholders in making informed decisions.

5.4. Risks

No additional risks have been identified for WP5.

6. Work package 6

6.1. Executive summary

Executive Summary	
Main results	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> SMARTIES seminar held on February 20th, 2025, with the sister projects BURST and SiLEAN. Website expanded by “News & Events” (blog)

DV#	Title	Status
D6.5	Report on clustering and alignment activities with other funded initiatives M18	Planned M18
D6.8	Plan of exploitation dissemination, and communication of results (PEDR) M18	Planned M18

MS#	Title	Status
No MS planned for reporting period M7 – M12, nor for M13 – M18.		

6.2. Tasks: Status

6.2.1. T6.1 Market analysis and circular business planning

Continuous monitoring of the PV market is ongoing and is planned for the entire TERASUN project. An updated version of the initial market analysis (D6.2) will be provided in M36, the *D6.7 Final, comprehensive PV market analysis*.

6.2.2. T6.2 Exploitation strategies and IPR management

IDE has outlined the initial exploitation strategy in *D6.3*, which serves as a framework for disseminating project results and ensuring their application and protection. This strategy details communication plans for stakeholders and will be updated at M18 and M36.

6.2.3. T6.3 Project identity and communication & dissemination activities

During the reporting period, the website was maintained and extended by an additional section “*News & Events*”. This section acts as the blog section of the TERASUN consortium, in which relevant information about achievements and upcoming events is published. Furthermore, the project consortium was actively disseminating via social media channels (*LinkedIn* and *X*). It was noticed during the M12 consortium meeting, that the number of followers on X stagnated for the last six months, while the number of followers increased on LinkedIn (+18%) as well as the impressions on the posts (+25%). The fact that the

activities on X do not pick up traction was discussed at the TERASUN CM M12 meeting and the consortium agreed that other dissemination channels will be evaluated to replace X.

6.2.4. T6.4 Gender and ethics dimension

The entire TERASUN consortium is committed to upholding the gender and ethics guidelines that were defined at the beginning of the project (D6.4), a commitment that stands for the duration of the project and beyond. In the current reporting period, no further actions were taken within T6.4.

6.2.5. T6.5 Synergies with other EU-funded projects

TERASUN established contact to the sister projects [BURST](#) and [SiLEAN](#) and formed the *Sustainable Materials And Research Towards Innovative Engineering Solutions for Silicon Solar Cells* (SMARTIES) cluster, supported by the creation of a dedicated communication channel. Furthermore, a joint seminar has been organised and held on February 20th, 2025. During the meeting *EU funding policy to PV projects and expected impacts* were presented followed by *Co-programmed partnership for Solar PV*. The three sister projects were presented to an international audience, along with the [PEPPERONI](#) project. This was followed by a Q&A session on the presentations and a panel discussion on the long-term European research strategy.

6.2.6. T6.6 Further impact and applications beyond the TERASUN project cycle

This task will start in M24.

Table 6 List of dissemination events.

Type	Event / author / title
Oral	IEEE PVSC 53, Montreal, June 2025 / Olindo Isabella / Novel c-Si Solar Cell Architectures for Achieving 28% Efficiency and Beyond
Poster	Silicon PV, Oxford, April 2025 / Roman Dvorak / Microscopic Characterization of SHJ Interdigitated Back-Contacts

6.3. Tasks: Outlook

- **T6.1:** Staying up to date with the evolution of the EU market situation
- **T6.2:** Continuous monitoring of exploitation opportunities to leverage the project results.
- **T6.3:** Continuous communication and dissemination of results via social media channels and the project website.
- **T6.4:** Continuous promotion of gender balance, equality and best practice
- **T6.5:** Joint organisation of events is envisioned within the SMARTIES cluster, i.e. together with the sister projects BURST and SiLEAN.
- **T6.6:** No activities planned yet

6.4. Risks

No additional risks have been identified for WP6.

Conclusions

The current report, *D1.15 Scientific & technical plan, execution report M7 – M12*, outlines the progress and key outcomes of work packages WP1 to WP6 up to month 12. The work accomplished thus far is notable and shows great promise for future progress, laying a solid groundwork for upcoming advancements in the project.

This deliverable is the second of a series of deliverables throughout the project and will be updated in *M26* (period M19-M24) and *M32* (period M25-M30). The remaining periods, i.e. M13-M18 and M31-M36, will be covered in the periodic reports.